

MEDIA SUITE

**FROM 2014 TO 2024
IN A SERIES
OF SHORT STORIES**

Authors: Roeland Ordelman, Julia Noordegraaf, Jasmijn van Gorp, Mari Wigham, Mary-Joy van der Deure

Team: Jasmijn van Gorp, Julia Noordegraaf, Roeland Ordelman, Johan Oomen, Norah Karrouche, Victor de Boer, Christian Olesen, Mari Wigham, Rana Klein, Jaap Blom, Willem Melder, Frank Sträter, Vincent Huis in 't Veld, Roosmarijn de Groot, Sara Veldhoen, Mary-Joy van der Deure, Meg Weijers, Divya Kanekal, Han Sloetjes, Paul Trilsbeek, Werner Helmich, Willemien Sanders, Emillie de Keulenaar, Alec Badenoch, Jasper Keijzer, Asli Ozgen-Havekotte, Megan Phipps, Liliana Melgar, Anne Helmond, Daniel Everts, Grietje Hoogland, Susan Aasman, Marijke De Valck, Berber Hagedoorn, Sanne Koevoets, Jeroen Salman, Sabrina Sauer, Andrea Meuzelaar, Berrie van der Molen, Vincent Baptist, Judith Keilbach, Marcel Broersma, Nanne van Noord, Sara Burkhardt, Vincent Kuitenbouwer, Eva Baaren, Tom Sloopweg, Iris van Vliet, Rosita Kiewik, Marijn Koolen, Hennie Brugman, Oana Inel, Lora Aroyo, Carlos Martínez Ortiz, Hugo Hurdeman, Thomas Poell, Kaspar Beelen, Bernhard Rieder, Susan Hoogervorst, Toine Pieters, Rob Wegter, Kathleen Lotze, Frank Harbers.

Contact: Roeland Ordelman

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AVResearcher prototype: distribution of words in different data sets

CoMeRDa	Aggregated search interface: exploratory research across various collections (television program descriptions, photos, Beeld & Geluid Wiki, broadcast guides, newspapers); visual representation of sources
AVResearcherXL	Exploring descriptions of radio and television programs, subtitles, and general newspaper articles. Facilitates comparative analysis of television programs and newspaper articles through visualizations like word clouds and timelines.
TROVe	A multimedia search engine that facilitates research into the dissemination of news via radio and television, Twitter, online newspapers, and blogs; provides insights into the development of public debates over time and across different media (identification of key topics, players, and impact through word clouds, line and scatter plots, and viewing data), with direct access to the items themselves.
DIVE	Presentation of collection items in context (linking to relevant contextual online information), facilitates intuitive browsing to delve deeper into the context.
Verteld Verleden	Exploratory and targeted searching in audiovisual narrative interview collections.

Description (anno 2014) of the projects that developed the prototypes that inspired Media Suite

INTRODUCTION

On Thursday, June 13, 2024, we celebrated the conclusion of the CLARIAH-Plus project. We looked back at what we have achieved with CLARIAH and looked forward to new collaborations, with the social sciences in SSHOC-NL and with the heritage domain through the Digital Heritage Network. And towards CLARIAH-NL as the organization that continues to sustainably promote the further development of the Dutch research infrastructure for the humanities.

For the Media Suite, developed in the CLARIAH-Plus program (2019-2024) and its predecessors CLARIAH-SEED (2014-2015) and CLARIAH-Core (2015-2019), another phase will come to a close. We began in 2014 by integrating five prototype tools (see adjacent page) from earlier projects into a 'Media Studies Suite.' The aim was to create a sustainable management, development, and production environment for these tools, providing researchers with a stable platform to conduct research with large datasets in the media domain, such as radio and television broadcasts, program guides, film, newspapers, oral history, and internet sources. After 10 years of intensive collaboration, we can proudly state that this goal has been achieved, and new horizons are now within reach.

With this 'CLARIAH Media Suite in a series of short stories,' we highlight the Media Suite from various perspectives, providing a summary of what the Media Suite offers researchers at the end of CLARIAH-Plus. Additionally, we briefly address the next phase, where we see several potential developments: improvements, new tools and datasets, and the broadening of the user group.

COLLABORATE

The development of the Media Suite for researchers has been organized as an interdisciplinary collaboration from the very beginning, involving humanities scholars, archivists, data specialists, computer scientists, and developers.

While working on earlier prototypes, it became clear that mutual understanding is essential to build something sustainable: understanding the technical possibilities and limitations, the context in which archives operate, and the methodological or practical considerations of research practices. Therefore, 'co-development' had to be central.

The Media Suite is embedded in the Labs Environment of the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision. This environment is designed to test new techniques and functionalities with the entire radio and television archive and users through an agile¹ approach. The development of the Media Suite was guided by educational workshops, design and evaluation sessions, and discussions based on the experiences of CLARIAH research fellows². Completed components are evaluated by a test panel, which has so far consisted mainly of project staff but will be expanded to include external users.

Furthermore, the development of a sustainable infrastructure around the Media Suite offers opportunities for constructive collaboration. Initiatives to make datasets available (through NDE, TDCC), apply image recognition (funded by CLICKNL), improve automatic speech recognition (within PDI-SSH projects), test audio fingerprinting techniques (in the AI4Media project), and enable investigative journalists to work in the Media Suite (BENEDMO project) are examples of this.

¹ An 'agile' approach focuses on phased improvements in collaboration with users through development cycles (sprints), with a key role for user evaluations.

² A CLARIAH Research Fellow conducts a small research project based on a clear research question, utilizing data and/or software that are part of the CLARIAH infrastructure. The goal is to test the infrastructure and identify opportunities for improvement.

Research use cases

- Cross-media analysis of the refugee crisis
- Historical research across (audio)visual and textual archives and collections
- Key point detection/pose analysis for Eye Jean Desmet collection
- Stories in Motion: Integrating oral histories into the Media Suite
- Historical research on media-events across heterogenous broadcast datasets
- Speech transcription of audiovisual data
- Tracing Re-use

User Stories: as a researcher, ...

- I want to be able to inspect the metadata of datasets and learn about completeness of metadata fields
- I want to filter my search results using facets that I can create myself based on available metadata fields
- I want to search for relevant material via speech transcripts or subtitles
- I want to find shots that are visually similar to the one that I am looking at
- I want to analyse the frequency of specific words mentioned over time in a dataset that I selected in the Media Suite

RECIPES

The Media Suite can be compared to a kitchen that provides the tools (facilities) to prepare meals (research results) with recipes (workflows), ingredients (data), and cookbooks (tutorials, learning materials, data & tool criticism). This metaphor serves as an instrument to communicate the desired direction. The explicit goal is to help and inspire the chefs in the kitchen of 'Digital Humanities.'

What needed to be included in this kitchen? The ability to perform advanced searches in large datasets (distant reading), compare results from different datasets, view individual items (close reading), annotate items, and save annotations, bookmarks, and search queries in a personal environment. And how should this be designed to fit seamlessly into the daily work of the researcher?

The Media Suite had to cater to the proverbial pizza maker, haute cuisine chef, and fusion artist among researchers. One could achieve quick results with simple tools, while another had more complex needs. Thus, the concept of 'recipes' was expanded, drawing inspiration from software development practices, to include use cases and user stories: a researcher has a specific research goal that the Media Suite can assist with (use case), involving a series of digital activities the researcher performs (user story) to achieve research results.

By collecting use cases, we gained a precise understanding of the needs of researchers in a digital research environment. For example, many researchers shared 'generic' desires, such as using tools to analyze audio (automatic speech recognition) and images (query-by-example), or employing Jupyter Notebooks to analyze the output of these tools. Naturally, researchers also wanted unlimited access to the data itself. Therefore, secure data access in the Media Suite was one of the first 'recipes' developed and implemented. This recipe, though it might seem mundane, significantly contributed to the success of the Media Suite.

While 'recipes' per se are no longer part of the Media Suite, they have shaped its development through use cases and user stories.

The screenshot shows the Clariah Datasets interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with filters for Organizations (15), Groups (4), and Tags (radio, television, audiovisual). The main content area shows a search for 'Nederlands Instituut voor Beeld en Geluid' resulting in 15 datasets found, ordered by Relevance. Two dataset entries are visible: 'Sound and Vision Archive - Radio' and 'Sound and Vision Archive', both with TSV and CSV download options.

The CKAN based dataset registry of the Media Suite

Distribution of programmes over series genres for TV

Number of programmes over time for TV

FINDABLE

Archives, libraries, and museums manage large amounts of data that are of interest to researchers. When a researcher is looking for existing datasets on a specific theme or topic, it would be helpful to have an online overview of these data. To address this need from researchers and others interested in datasets, dataset registries are being developed. Within the heritage sector, the NDE dataset registry³ has been developed, and for researchers, INEO⁴, the community portal of CLARIAH, provides an overview of datasets collected in the CLARIAH dataset registry.

Having multiple types of registries where datasets can be found is not a problem. As long as all these registries are kept up-to-date in the same way and continue to refer to the same datasets, it is actually a crucial condition for facilitating different types of users from diverse communities in their search for relevant data through their preferred registry.

At the start of the Media Suite developments, there were no suitable data registries available, so we developed our own registry to allow users to find the datasets that can be accessed through the Media Suite. We implemented this registry using the open-source data management system CKAN⁵.

Researchers have indicated during workshops that the Media Suite data registry is not only useful for discovering which collections can be accessed in the Media Suite but also for finding detailed information at the dataset level. This information can include substantive aspects of the dataset (e.g., topics discussed) or characteristics of the dataset, such as the distribution over time or the distribution of genres for the Sound & Vision catalog. See adjacent examples of dataset visualizations in the Media Suite data registry, in this instance from the Sound & Vision catalog as a dataset⁶.

³ <https://datasetregister.netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl>

⁴ <https://www.ineo.tools>

⁵ <https://ckan.org>

⁶ <https://mediasuitedata.clariah.nl/dataset/audiovisual-collection-daan>

Field	Level	Description	Type	Completeness	
Carrier collection ID	program	Actual value of the collectionid field	text	7.33%	Select
Carrier collection ID	program	Not used, contains related information to the collectionid	keyword	31.96%	Select
Carrier collection number	program	Collection number of the audiovisual entity on the carrier	keyword	31.96%	Select
Carrier collection title	program	Collection title of the audiovisual entity on the carrier	text	31.96%	Select
Carrier colour	program	Whether or not the audiovisual entity on the carrier is in color	keyword	18.53%	Select
Carrier colour space	program	The colorspace of an audiovisual entity on the carrier	keyword	0.05%	Select
Carrier compression	program	Compression format of the carrier containing an audiovisual entity	keyword	0.42%	Select
Carrier created by	program	The creator of the audiovisual entity on the carrier	text	74.26%	Select
Carrier creation date	program	Date on which the carrier (containing an audiovisual entity) was entered in the Sound and Vision database	date	97.46%	Select
Carrier depositor	program	Depositor of the carrier containing an audiovisual entity	text	31.96%	Select
Carrier depot state	program	Availability of the carrier (containing an audiovisual entity) in the Sound and Vision depot	keyword	55.79%	Select
Carrier depot state explanation	program	Additional information about the availability of the carrier in the Sound and Vision depot	keyword	3.15%	Select
Carrier digital born	program	Whether or not the audiovisual entity flowed in digital or if there are any non-digital materials	keyword	66.75%	Select
Carrier ext. checksum	program	Checksum of the carrier (used for detecting errors on the carrier)	keyword	1.91%	Select
Carrier file size	program	File size of the carrier containing an audiovisual entity	keyword	10.74%	Select

The Collection Inspector describes the metadata fields and their coverage

A visualisation of the coverage of a metadata field over time

DATASETS

The Media Suite provides access to 92 collections from a variety of institutions. These include the Sound & Vision archive, the newspaper archive of the KB (via Delpher), oral history interviews stored at DANS, the audio collection of the Meertens Institute, and films from the Eye Filmmuseum.

A significant collection within the Media Suite is the radio and television archive of Sound & Vision. This includes related datasets such as broadcasting guides, audience ratings, and datasets stored by Sound & Vision as part of their archival services (like archived parliamentary meetings). Recent broadcasts are available for research with a few days' delay.

Audience ratings are a valuable resource for studying the history of public radio and television consumption and experience. CLARIAH has contributed to the digitization and availability of this collection to researchers through market research institute GfK⁷. Broadcasting guides were previously made available in the Metamorfose program (also accessible via Delpher⁸). Additionally, CLARIAH has facilitated access to the film and audio collections of the World Broadcasting Archive, and the Desmet and Peter Rubin collections at the Eye Filmmuseum.

These datasets are diverse in size, media type, formats used, and the granularity of metadata. Integrating these datasets into the Media Suite has required significant effort, both from the Media Suite team and the data-managing institutions like DANS and the Eye Filmmuseum.

A critical part of the research methodology for working with these datasets is the ability to scrutinize the underlying structure of a dataset: understanding its data model and the coverage of various metadata fields. For this purpose, the Media Suite includes the Collection Inspector⁹ (see adjacent), which allows researchers to delve into the details of the datasets.

⁷ <https://nieuws.beeldengeluid.nl/168651-gfk-draagt-archief-kijk-en-luistercijfers-over-aan-beeld-en-geluid>

⁸ <https://www.delpher.nl/nl/tijdschriften/>

⁹ <https://mediasuite.clariah.nl/tool/collection-inspector?cids=daan-catalogue-aggr>

Toast to the availability of Audience Ratings from left to right Eppo van Nispen tot Sevenaer (Sound & Vision), Julia Noordegraaf (UvA, CLARIAH) en Liesbeth Nekkers (GfK)

Nepnieuwsdiscours 2014 - 2022

Woorden uit het nepnieuwsdiscours

Examples of visualizations of quantitative data analysis on large-scale datasets, in this case the rise of the fake news discourse (Luuk Ex and Willemien Sanders).

ACCESSING DATA

A significant portion of the data in the Media Suite is restricted due to copyright or privacy considerations. This means that the material cannot be accessed by just anyone, let alone downloaded.

For the radio and television broadcasts of the Dutch Public Broadcaster (NPO) in the Sound & Vision archive, this material can be made available for research purposes. Researchers can access, listen to, and annotate this data within the Media Suite environment by logging in with a student or staff account from a Dutch university or college. However, downloading (meta)data is not possible.

 The ability for researchers to log in was one of the initial priorities for the Media Suite. Within CLARIAH, the decision was made to leverage SURFconext¹⁰, which allows institutions connected to SURF (the collaborative ICT organization for Dutch education and research) to use a single account (Single Sign-On) across various services offered in the research field, such as the Media Suite.

A small but steadily growing group of researchers showed significant interest in a more quantitative approach to (large-scale) data. This involves searching for patterns, such as identifying which politicians speak the most on television during an election campaign¹¹, or examining the rise of fake news discourse in the media¹². To address such questions, researchers prefer working directly with the data itself rather than through a graphical user interface like the Media Suite. For instance, they use tools like Jupyter Notebooks to query and manipulate data (end-points, APIs) to uncover and visualize patterns.

In collaboration with SURF and researchers from the social sciences (ODISSEI), the SANE concept was developed: datasets are made available in a closed, temporary environment. After the research is completed, the environment is dismantled, ensuring that data-managing institutions retain full control over their data. This technology is currently undergoing significant refinement, including within the SSHOC-NL project. In the near future, SANE will make it much simpler for researchers to independently analyze large datasets.

¹⁰ <https://wiki.surfnet.nl/display/surfconextdev>

¹¹ <https://mediasuitedatastories.clariah.nl/elections-2021-first-results/>

¹² <https://mediasuitedatastories.clariah.nl/fake-news-2023/>

Dataset Archaeology example: timeline showing metadata fractures (vertical lines) for the Sound & Vision collection including significant changes (dots).

Model\Dataset	bn_nl	cts_nl	bn_vl	cts_vl
Kaldi_NL	12.6%	38.6%	21.2%	59.4%
Whisper v2	12.7%	25.9%	-	-
Whisper v3	13.7%	28.1%	-	-
Whisper v2 w/ VAD	11.6%	25.3%	-	-
Whisper v3 w/ VAD	14.1%	26.5%	-	-
faster-whisper v2	10.6%	24.1%	13.0%	38.5%
faster-whisper v3	12.5%	25.5%	14.9%	38.4%
faster-whisper v2 w/ VAD	10.0%	23.9%	13.6%	37.9%
faster-whisper v3 w/ VAD	12.3%	25.1%	14.6%	36.9%
XLS-R FT on Dutch	14.8%	33.5%	17.0%	51.7%
MMS - 102 languages	23.4%	49.0%	25.0%	64.2%
MMS - 1162 languages	18.5%	42.7%	19.4%	57.7%

Quality of automatic speech recognition from various recognizers for speech types (bn = broadcast news, cts = conversation, nl= Dutch, vl=flemish)

CRITICAL ABOUT DATA & TOOLS

For a researcher, background information on the origins of large datasets such as the Sound & Vision collection is methodologically crucial. Over the years, various decisions have been made during the development of a dataset that have shaped its final appearance in a research environment like the Media Suite. These decisions include changes in collection policies (what to archive and to what extent), major digitization initiatives like Sound & Vision's Images for the Future¹³, and policies regarding manual and automatic metadata creation.

The process of uncovering these kinds of decisions around a dataset is often referred to as "Dataset Archaeology," as this knowledge often needs to be excavated from old documentation or, if unavailable, from the memories of archivists and curators.

The decisions made about a dataset can significantly impact the analyses conducted. Gaps in archived genres can distort the portrayal of the broadcasting landscape during a specific period. The absence of descriptive metadata, common in radio materials, may mean that part of the dataset is excluded from the analysis. This is not inherently problematic as long as researchers are aware and take this into account when interpreting their data analyses—in other words, being critical of the datasets they use. To support Data Criticism, more of this archaeological information is gradually being added to dataset descriptions in the Media Suite dataset registry. For the Sound & Vision collection, a thorough analysis has been conducted on metadata fractures¹⁴, and information for each dataset in the collection is gathered in a data portal¹⁵.

Tools also have a profound impact on the outcomes researchers observe. How a search algorithm is configured or how well a speech recognizer performs can determine what a researcher discovers and incorporates into an analysis. Therefore, Tool Criticism is equally important. The Media Suite supports this by striving to be transparent in its documentation about the choices made during development or for automatic metadata generation¹⁶ (see adjacent), and the implications these choices have for users.

¹³ <https://publications.beeldengeluid.nl/pub/17>

¹⁴ <https://data.beeldengeluid.nl/nl/showcases/data-fractures>

¹⁵ <https://data.beeldengeluid.nl>

¹⁶ https://opensource-spraakherkenning-nl.github.io/ASR_NL_results

The screenshot shows the 'Resource Viewer' interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Data', 'Tools', 'Workspace', and 'Data Stories'. The main area features a video player for 'NIEUWSUUR' with a 'DRUGSLAB' logo. Below the video is a search bar and a timeline with segments. On the right, a 'Content Annotations' panel lists transcript segments with timestamps and text. The interface includes navigation buttons like 'Back to results' and 'Bookmark'.

Using speech transcripts (on the right), you can also search within an item

The screenshot shows the 'Similarity' interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'VisXP-test'. The main area features a video player for 'SPORTJOURNAAL: NOS Sportjournaal (2009) 2009-01-02'. Below the video is a search bar and a timeline with segments. On the right, a 'Content Annotations' panel lists transcript segments with timestamps and text. The interface includes navigation buttons like 'Back to results' and 'Open in Resource Viewer'.

Searching for visually similar images (on the right) given an example (top left)

SPOKEN WORD AND IMAGES

When searching through large amounts of data, the availability of descriptive metadata is crucial, especially for audiovisual data, sound (samples), and images (pixels). Within an archive, the metadata for individual archival items varies widely. Some items are extensively described manually by archivists, while often the information is very limited and may even lack a title.

A transcript of the spoken word in a video or audio clip provides an alternative method to search audiovisual archival material and conduct quantitative analyses across multiple archive items. For example, researchers are keenly interested in subtitles for this reason, or if those are unavailable, as is the case with radio and older television programs, in transcripts generated by automatic speech recognition.

In the Media Suite infrastructure, datasets can be processed through automatic speech recognition. Due to the vast amount of data, priority is given to radio programs and Oral History, which are otherwise challenging to search, as well as genres like news and current affairs, which are frequently requested for research purposes. Ultimately, all data within the Media Suite will be accessible through speech recognition technology.

The quality of speech recognition is an important consideration. To select the speech recognizer to be used and also to inform researchers about the quality of speech recognition (see also data and tool criticism above), evaluations are conducted in so-called benchmarks. These benchmarks demonstrate how well speech recognizers perform on different types of data.

In addition to spoken word, the visuals in AV materials are an intriguing source of information that typically receives minimal description in metadata.

Automatic image

recognition offers opportunities to visually unlock this material. Soon, researchers in the Media Suite will be able to search based on similarity: given a shot, such as an iconic image related to climate change, they will be shown video clips that resemble it.

The screenshot shows a search interface for the 'Sound and Vision Archive'. The search query is "oorlog AND (duitsland OR rusland)". The results are filtered by 'mediaType' to 'audio', showing 69,706 results. A dropdown menu is open, highlighting 'Speech transcripts (ASR)'. Below the menu, a snippet of a search result is visible, titled 'Toespraak koningin Wilhelmina over mobilisatie en neutraliteitsverklaring'.

Advanced Search: by material type (audio), in spoken word, with Boolean operators

Interactive visualizations of search results: filtering by year using the bar chart

The screenshot shows a search interface with a list of search results for the query 'kroes'. The results include names like 'Kroes, B.', 'Kroes, Ole (acteur)', and 'Kroes, Neelie (politicus Nederland VVD oud-min.)'. A detailed view of a person's information is shown, including a photo of Neelie Kroes and a 'Person information' pop-up window. The pop-up window contains a search bar and links to view the person in the GTAA and Wikidata. The main interface also shows a 'Metadata' panel with details about the record, such as the title 'EENVANDAAG', the date '2016-06-24', and the description.

Linked data as applied within the search process: additional information and searching for persons

SEARCH

Searching within 92 collections plays a central role within the Media Suite. For researchers, the simplicity of everyday search engines is not sufficient. More than just 'question-answer', researchers aim to find relevant 'bits-and-pieces' within the vast amount of data. It involves bringing together and analyzing fragments of information that can lead to new insights. Researchers require **advanced** search options: within a specific time period, for a particular type of material, involving individuals in specific roles, based on title or spoken words, and so on.

The Media Suite allows searching for **terms** within metadata. Boolean operators are supported to create more complex queries. For example: "war AND (Germany OR Russia)". Additionally, a user can specify which metadata field or group of metadata fields to search within. For instance, only in titles or in persons. The Beeld & Geluid **thesaurus**, GTAA¹⁷, with lists of standard terms is used to provide autocomplete options for personal names and to disambiguate individuals with the same name, ensuring users can search for the correct person. **Filters** can be applied per collection, for example, because the user wants only video material and no audio. In addition to the standard filters for a collection, users can select relevant filters from a list of suitable metadata fields in the collection. **Interactive visualizations** of search results, such as the distribution of results over time in a bar chart (see adjacent page), can be a useful tool to filter search results by year with a single click.

In the Beeld & Geluid collection, **linked data** is used to provide additional information for individuals through links to external sources such as the GTAA thesaurus or Wikidata. When viewing a resource, users can see which other individuals are related to that resource. Additional information about these individuals can be easily accessed, and users can also directly search for other resources in the collection where these individuals appear.

Search **queries** can be viewed as representations of virtual datasets or research corpora defined by a researcher. The researcher can save these queries in a personal workspace within the Media Suite for future reuse or for sharing with others. Another capability is to compare datasets using queries, for example, to analyze how frequently the word 'Europe' is mentioned in newspapers versus on television.

¹⁷ <https://www.beeldengeluid.nl/kennis/kennisthemas/metadata/gemeenschappelijke-thesaurus-audiovisuele-archieven>

The still rudimentary Media Suite Resource Viewer in 2018

The extensive recent version of the Media Suite Resource Viewer

VIEW AND ANNOTATE

The Media Suite was developed with the idea of creating a user-friendly environment to support researchers in their work. While an increasing number of (young) researchers are starting to code themselves, not every researcher finds it easy to navigate the digital landscape. Additionally, for a significant portion of (media) research, the ability to view and annotate the data itself is crucial. This requires a user interface that enables logging in, playback, clipping, saving, annotating, and sharing.

Throughout the development of the Media Suite, considerable attention has been paid to the user experience (UX) of researchers through design sessions, an agile work methodology, and a test panel. A prime example of how the Media Suite's components are developed is the creation of the '**Resource Viewer**.' This feature allows researchers to view and interact with individual sources, facilitating the 'close reading' part of their workflow.

Based on research¹⁸ into what an interface for audiovisual media research should look like, significant progress has been made over the past few years. The images alongside show the evolution of the Resource Viewer from 2018 to the present day. In 2018, the visibility of available metadata, navigation options, and annotation features were quite rudimentary. The latest version, however, offers significantly enhanced capabilities for viewing metadata.

Researchers can bookmark interesting sources for easy retrieval later. For more detailed notes during **close reading**, they can create **annotations** with keywords, comments, and external links. This can be done within existing **segments** or segments created by the researcher. For scanned texts and images, researchers can annotate the entire image or select specific parts to annotate.

Navigating through the material is straightforward using the horizontal timeline/segment view or the vertical annotation view (such as scrolling through speech segments), depending on the researcher's preference. In the user's personal **workspace**, all bookmarks, annotations, and saved queries are stored for easy access.

¹⁸ Hurdeman, H. C., Melgar-Estrada, L-M., Ordelman, R., & Noordegraaf, J. (2019). Supporting the Interpretation of Enriched Audiovisual Sources through Temporal Content Exploration. In *Digital Humanities Benelux Conference 2019*.

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Publieke omroep heeft uitgesproken voorkeur voor rechtse mannen

Made with Flourish
 Figuur 2.6. Totale herkenning van politici in seconden, verdeeld over het politieke spectrum.

Woorden uit het nepnieuwscours

DATA STORIES

In addition to the scholarly publications we maintain in a Zotero group¹⁹, the Media Suite offers two accessible ways to communicate research projects to interested audiences: blogs and data stories. Since publishing through academic channels can have a long lead time, **blogs**²⁰ and **data stories**²¹ provide a useful means to quickly and easily bridge the gap between the research field and traditional news media as well as social media discussions.

Blogs offer researchers opportunities to communicate their work from various perspectives, ranging from announcing new research projects to presenting findings. For research involving data in the Media Suite, it is beneficial to link directly to the data itself. A narrative is much more compelling when hypotheses are supported with **visualizations** and **data references**. Making the underlying data accessible aligns well with the desire — both in research and societal discussions — for **transparency** in the research process. It also supports the goal of making research data comply with the **FAIR** principles: findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (reproducible and verifiable).

The concept of data stories in the Media Suite refers to narratives based on the **quantitative analysis** of often large datasets, using custom-written code in a programming environment, such as Jupyter Notebooks²². Examples include an analysis of all news broadcasts over the past 20 years or all episodes of a specific current affairs program, or even a combination of various data sources. For instance, a data story has been published about the media discourse on fake news and how news programs have reported on viruses like HIV, SARS, and COVID-19²³ over the years. Such data stories have also captured the interest of investigative journalists, leading to a publication²⁴ based on a data story about the politicians who appeared in the media in the lead-up to the 2021 elections.

¹⁹ https://www.zotero.org/groups/2288915/media_studies_clariah_wp5

²⁰ [h https://mediasuite.clariah.nl/blog](https://mediasuite.clariah.nl/blog)

²¹ <https://mediasuitedatastories.clariah.nl/>

²² <https://jupyter.org/>

²³ <https://mediasuitedatastories.clariah.nl/covid-19/>

²⁴ <https://nos.nl/artikel/2372814-onderzoek-rechts-domineert-de-verkiezingscampagne-op-radio-en-tv>

CLARIAH WP5 Output 2015-2024 (N=404)

RESEARCH

The Media Suite has enabled new and innovative research. To date, it has generated over **400 publications, presentations, and tutorials**²⁵ from CLARIAH Research²⁶ and Teaching Fellows, researchers involved in externally funded projects, PhD candidates, and thesis students. In the project's initial phase (2015-2018), many publications focused on the development of the Media Suite, **qualitative annotation methods**, **digital tools** for film studies, and **media archaeology** of the digital interface of its predecessor, AVResearcher.

After the Media Suite became fully operational and its usage more widespread, a second trend emerged in publications. From 2019 to 2022, the focus shifted more towards research methods and heuristics, such as **source criticism**. During this same period, a large group of Research Fellows began their work, culminating in a special issue of the *Tijdschrift voor Mediageschiedenis*²⁷ on involving researchers in the development of research infrastructure.

More recently, we have entered a new phase. With more materials available and the implementation of Jupyter Notebooks, the focus of publications since 2023 has shifted towards more **substantive analyses of media**. PhD candidates have completed dissertations on using speech transcripts in research or are working on Twitter collections. Sister projects of CLARIAH, such as PDI-SSH SANE, PDI-SSH Twi-XL, and VisXP (CLICKNL²⁸), have brought additional attention to infrastructure development focused on **data science**.

To highlight research conducted with the Media Suite, numerous **national and international** activities have been organized. For instance, following the launch of CLARIAH-CORE, a **summer school** was held where five interdisciplinary teams of researchers worked with the newly launched stable version of the Media Suite. Additionally, various **workshops** have been aimed at researchers and other interested parties, such as research journalists, as part of the "Data-als-Kans²⁹" series. Internationally, workshops have been conducted at the annual Digital Humanities Conferences and DHBenelux.

²⁵ https://www.zotero.org/groups/2288915/media_studies_clariah_wp5/library

²⁶ CLARIAH Research Fellows conduct research using the CLARIAH research infrastructure under construction, such as the Media Suite, to validate it and inform developers about bottlenecks and additional needs.

²⁷ <https://tmgonline.nl/53/volume/24/issue/1-2>

²⁸ <https://www.clicknl.nl/en/>

²⁹ <https://www.beeldengeluid.nl/kennis/data-als-kans>

Collection Inspector

The purpose of this tool is to provide an overview of how a collection dataset is constituted and also to allow a closer inspection of their metadata (e.g., detect incomplete data, or observe value distributions along date fields).

It is important to have clear that the collection inspector does not give search results. Future developments include the integration of other metrics (besides completeness) for the evaluation of metadata quality, and the possibility to visualize metadata completeness together with search results.

How to use

1. When you open the Inspect tool you will find a button to add a Collection. This opens the "Collection selector," where you can see the available collections (see [FAQ section: What kind of data is available via the Media Suite?](#))
2. When you select a collection, you can inspect its metadata fields by clicking on "Select field to analyse"
3. In this graphic you can see the completeness of ONE metadata field over time. The timeline chart uses a date field selected by the user. Be aware that these date fields are also metadata, and that they can also be more or less complete. You can evaluate the completeness of a date field as well, using the first option in Step 1.

Workspace

Typically, researchers perform a variety of tasks in the Media Suite, such as formulating queries for searching collections, creating their own 'virtual collections', and making annotations. The Media Suite offers a "virtual Workspace" to allow researchers to save their work. The workspace thus provides researchers with possibilities to manage their research process and enable transparency of the process.

The Workspace supports the following functions:

- Organising work in User Projects
- Adding personal collections to the Workspace to apply Media Suite functions such as search and annotation
- Programming with data using Jupyter Notebooks (only limitedly available)

In the Figure below, an overview of these functions is presented:

User Projects

In the Media Suite, a User project is defined as a container for storing personal corpora and annotations created during search and analysis of the data available in the Media Suite. Some of the Qualitative Data Analysis (QDA) typically used by researchers, refer to user projects as "hermeneutic units" (in Atlas.ti) or "Projects" (in NVIVO).

In the Media Suite, for instance, a researcher can create a user project for a topic or for a research question, which will help her/him, among others, to:

- Group together entire items or fragments for creating a corpus (the so-called "bookmarks").
- Add and retrieve manual annotations
- Store and compare saved queries
- Keep track of her/his browsing history (the so-called "navigation paths" in the Exploratory tool)
- Take screenshots of "tool sessions" (in Version 4 only available in the Exploratory tool).

LEARN

During the development of the Media Suite, **user-friendliness** has been a key focus. However, the vast amount of data, variety of tools, and researchers' desire to tailor functionalities to their individual workflows or the methodologies of their disciplines mean that researchers must invest time in **learning** how to navigate the capabilities and limitations of the Media Suite.

Conducting workshops is one way to familiarize users with the Media Suite, but for everyday use, **manuals, help functions, and tutorials** are indispensable. Over the years, the Media Suite has evolved significantly in this regard, leading to a functional distinction between various ways of learning to work with the Media Suite.

Practical questions about usage are grouped in a "**Help**" menu, divided into sections such as "Quick Start Guide," "How To," "FAQ," "Troubleshooting," and "Release Notes." This menu also provides direct contact options for addressing issues with the Media Suite via communication channels like the community platform Gitter³⁰, which is used for reporting bugs. For users' convenience, different parts of the Media Suite offer one-click access to relevant information (as shown in the example next to this text about using the Collection Inspector and the Workspace).

To make the Media Suite accessible within a research scenario or an educational environment, another form of documentation is indispensable: the **tutorial**. Tutorials are available through the "Learn" menu. These tutorials focus on specific tools as well as topics like creating data visualizations, using viewing and listening figures, and exploring international data sets in the Media Suite. Many of these tutorials are specifically developed to serve as **teaching materials**. The tutorials are also sustainably stored (via Zenodo), allowing them to reach users through "course registries" nationally (INEO) and internationally (e.g., via DARIAH³¹ and CLARIN).

Creating documentation often goes underappreciated and involves a lot of manual work. Keeping documentation up-to-date is also a challenge. However, it is an **essential** part of supporting researchers and promoting the use of digital infrastructure.

³⁰ <https://gitter.im>

³¹ <https://dhcr.clarin-dariah.eu/>

Joint ODISSEI/CLARIAH presentation on SANE during the SURF Research Day 2024

INFRASTRUCTURE

The Media Suite is often described as a virtual research environment, a “portal” where researchers can conduct media collection research. Behind the scenes, there are complex processes that researchers ideally remain unaware of but are crucial for the Media Suite’s functionality. In other words, the Media Suite is the visible end product, built on a relatively invisible **digital infrastructure** comprising multiple components.

Primarily, the Media Suite is connected to the infrastructure of Beeld & Geluid. This connection, through **APIs**, allows for the harvesting and indexing of all metadata for searchability, content streaming, executing linked data queries, and supporting large-scale data processes via local servers and cloud services like AWS. These processes require significant computational power for tasks such as quick search executions and automated speech or image recognition. Organizing, developing, and managing these technical processes 'under the hood' is complex, particularly because the components of the engine running the Media Suite need to be as **sustainable** as possible: robust and future-proof, yet manageable with the relatively limited technical manpower available.

The integration of the Media Suite with **national infrastructures** ensures that we can sustainably provide the desired facilities through collaboration. The CLARIAH infrastructure, for instance, enables standardized annotations that can be sustainably stored and shared through the **annotation infrastructure** developed and maintained by the Humanities Cluster. Oral History interviews can be viewed in the Media Suite thanks to **data infrastructures** provided by SURF and DANS. More broadly, the infrastructure for the social and humanities sciences, which we are developing with **ODISSEI** within the **SSHOC-NL** project, helps us work with SURF to develop services for using sensitive data (copyright, privacy) for research and to employ supercomputers to meet emerging demands for AI applications in research.

Lastly, the importance of collaboration around **digital heritage infrastructure**, coordinated through the Network Digitaal Erfgoed (NDE), cannot be overstated. From both a technical perspective (linked data, data registers) and a content perspective, this collaboration is essential for making the many rich heritage datasets FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

Future: sharing annotations within CLARIAH

Collections for research can be managed and made available through the Media Suite via archival services (archiefdiensten@beeldengeluid.nl).

FUTURE

Celebrating 10 years of the Media Suite has been quite a journey, evolving from mere ideas and ambitions into a tangible instrument that supports researchers. This journey has been marked by discussions, mutual understanding, weighing decisions, learning, and making progress together. It has seen colleagues come and go, each contributing to a robust structure that is now ready for the next phase. There are plenty of ideas for improvements, refinements, new tools and datasets, and new entry points for diverse users, including research journalists and citizen scientists.

Several plans are clearly taking shape or already underway. One significant direction is providing researchers with more options for data science-oriented **quantitative analyses** of large datasets. **Safe access** and the integration of more heritage datasets are key components of this direction. Over the next few years, there will be an increasing focus on applying **artificial intelligence** (AI) or even training specific AI models to answer research questions. Facilitating the seamless movement between qualitative and quantitative methods within the Media Suite will be part of this initiative.

Another area being developed within the CLARIAH-Plus project is a revision of the **annotation** process and the connected **personal workspace** in the Media Suite. There is a strong demand for the ability to share annotations or transfer them to other environments within the CLARIAH infrastructure. Additionally, the concept of **personal research corpora**, composed of parts from multiple datasets across different data custodians and media types, is gaining traction. Ideas include creating a **digital rolodex** as a workspace to persistently store personal datasets and annotations. There are also plans to enhance annotation capabilities to better facilitate **polyvocality** and **reflection** on sources.

Regarding datasets and tooling, there is a need for improved capabilities to compare information across different datasets, thereby enhancing **transmedia** research. While this is currently possible within the Media Suite, there is room for further development. Additionally, expanding the availability of datasets in the Media Suite remains a priority. Desired additions include more **Oral History** collections, **regional** archives, **international** datasets like EUScreen, and **social media** datasets. Lastly, in collaboration with Beeld & Geluid, there are plans to develop a CLARIAH-NDE **archiving service** to make collections available in the Media Suite.

BEEELD & GELUID

**Download Media Suite
Brochure on Zenodo**

